

FINANCING MEDICINE AND SUPPLIES IN SINDH PROVINCE IN PAKISTAN

KEY TAKEAWAYS

In Pakistan, health is a devolved subject managed independently at the sub-national level following the passage of the 18th Constitutional Amendment in 2010. This gives each province authority over their healthcare systems, including medicine and supplies procurement. As a result, each province has developed its own unique practices for procuring essential health supplies – contextualized to local needs, resources, and administrative frameworks.

This factsheet focuses specifically on the procurement and financing practices in Pakistan's province of Sindh. It looks at the procurement process, financial flow, budgeting and utilization, as well as the bottlenecks and limitations of the overall procurement landscape for essential medicines and health supplies (EMHS) in the province of Sindh.

Sindh's procurement landscape for EMHS involves participation and oversight from multiple parties. EMHS in Sindh are funded by the provincial government. There are a few ongoing initiatives, where development partners partly manage the medicines supplies through in-kind support. However, the administrative arrangements, resources envelope, procurements practices for those vertical programs are beyond the scope of this factsheet

KEY ACTORS

Department of Finance (FD)

Responsible for approving and rationalizing medicine and supplies budget proposed by Department of Health

Department of Health (DoH)

Responsible for consolidating Annual Procurement Plan for EMHS as well as consolidating budget demands. After receiving funds from Finance Dep, allocates share of budget for the medicine and supplies of all health facilities.

Director General Health Services (DGHS)

Process owner of procurement in Health department, has Procurement Monitoring & Inspection (PM&I) Cell to initiate and oversee the entire procurement process

Secondary Healthcare Facilities (SHCFs)

Secondary healthcare facilities are headed by Medical Superintendents (MS). They issue purchase orders but procurement management is done by the CPC .

Tertiary Health Facilities (THFs)

Tertiary level facilities are headed by Medical Superintendents/ Chief Executives. They are also independent procuring system.

Drug Testing Labs (DTLs)

District Drug Inspectors collect and inspect samples from DHOs and facilities where medicines and supplies are delivered, and issue clearance reports.

Pre-qualified Suppliers

Usually selected by the CPC (for routine purchase system) and by UPCs (for local purchase system). Upon receiving of orders from DHO/DDOs, they must ensure the supply of quality medicine timely

Sindh Public Procurement Authority (SPPRA)

Regulatory body for procurement in public sectors across the province, set up in 2010

KEY ACTORS

District Health Officers (DHOs)

DHOs serve as procuring entities on behalf of PHC facilities, placing Purchase Orders for EMHS at standardized rates and managing their storage and delivery to district facilities. They manage the intra-district and inter-district borrowing of supplies. They also have the mandate to purchase the supplies through 'Local Purchase mechanism', remaining within the ceiling of 15% of budget of supplies/ medicines.

Central Procurement Committee (CPC)

Constituted at the provincial level and has the mandate of bid invitation, bid evaluation, contracting, setting price, etc.

PM&I cell serves as the secretariat for the CPC, which develops Standard Bidding Documents (SBD) along with criteria for evaluations, develops technical specifications of the needed items and does M&E. It is responsible for contracting out the unit rates for the specified EMHS to the suppliers. Purchasing entities must use the list of selected items by CPC. The CPC practices a centralized contracting process for selected EMHS through a competitive bidding process.

Unified Procurement Committee (UPC) for Local Purchase of Drugs/Medicines

There is also a unified procurement committee constituted for procurement of drugs/ medicines through local purchasing up to 15% ceiling of the respective approved budget.

UPCs are chaired by DHOs, Medical Superintendents, Divisional Directors (depending on the type of facilities doing procurement)

As shown on the next page, the system in Sindh operates via **two distinct channels for medicine procurement and distribution**, depending on whether facilities have their own Drawing and Disbursing Officer (DDO).

FOR FACILITIES WITH DDOS

The process begins with their DDOs estimating annual supply needs and submitting budget requests to the Finance Department (FD) through the Health Department. Once approved, the FD directly releases the supplies budget to these facilities on a quarterly basis. These facilities can independently issue purchase orders to suppliers who are pre-qualified by either the central procurement committee or unified procurement committee. Facilities pay them directly upon receiving and inspecting the supplies.

FOR FACILITIES WITHOUT DDOS

The District Health Office (DHO) takes a more central role. With few exceptions, all PHC facilities do not have DDOs. These facilities submit monthly supply requests to their DHO, that estimates their annual needs. The DHO consolidates the supply needs for all facilities in their district (both with and without DDO) and submits a comprehensive budget request to the FD via the Health Department. The FD then releases the budget to DHOs on a quarterly basis. For these non-DDO facilities, the DHO handles procurement by issuing purchase orders to pre-qualified suppliers, receiving and inspecting supplies, making payments, and distributing supplies to facilities on a monthly basis.

The DGHS Central Procurement Committee (CPC) plays a crucial role by managing the supplier pre-qualification process through competitive bidding. Once suppliers are pre-qualified, the CPC shares their list with both DHOs and DDO-equipped facilities. To provide flexibility in the system, both DHOs and facilities with DDOs can use up to 15% of their supplies budget to purchase from alternative suppliers, though these purchases require committee approval. This alternative procurement channel helps address emergency needs or supply gaps.

FINANCING EMHS IN DISTRICTS WHERE THE DHO IS THE MAIN PROCUREMENT UNIT

The diagram below provides information on the procuring entities, procurement processes and the fund flow mechanisms in place for the procurement of medicines and supplies in Sindh. The system is interconnected through three main types of flows: funds (from the Finance Department), commodities (from suppliers to facilities), and information (between various actors for coordination and reporting purposes).

Funds → Commodities → Information →

FACILITY AUTONOMY

In Sindh, the authority to procure EMHS is fragmented across different administrative levels and units. The procurement system varies significantly between primary and secondary healthcare facilities, with distinct mechanisms for government-managed and PPHI-operated facilities.

For government-managed facilities, District Health Officers (DHOs) oversee procurement for primary healthcare facilities, while secondary healthcare facilities have partial procurement autonomy. Secondary facilities can make local purchases up to 15% of their medicine budget through unified procurement committees, particularly in cases of stockouts or delays in delivery from CPC-contracted suppliers. However, these facilities lack revenue retention mechanisms, and any unutilized funds must be surrendered to the treasury. Primary care facilities under direct government management have no autonomous purchasing authority.

This mixed system of centralized and decentralized procurement authorities, combined with varying levels of financial autonomy, creates a complex landscape for medicine and supply management in Sindh's public health sector.

	DHOs	Tertiary HFs	Secondary HFs	Primary HFs
Autonomy to Order Supplies	✓	✓	✓	✗
Autonomy to Pay Suppliers	✓	✓	✓	✗
Autonomy to Procure Emergency Medicine Locally ¹	✓	✓	✓	✗

MEDICINES AND SUPPLIES AT PPHI-MANAGED FACILITIES

The Peoples' Primary Healthcare Initiative (PPHI) in Pakistan, launched in 2005, focuses on improving access to PHC services through Public Private Partnerships (PPPs), particularly in Basic Health Units (BHUs), dispensaries, and Maternal and Child Health (MCH) centers. PPHI Sindh manages most PHC facilities and some secondary facilities through a provincial outsourcing arrangement. As a section 42 company¹, it receives a single-line grant from the Sindh Government, providing financial autonomy while still following SPPRA procurement rules.

PPHI's procurement system for EMHS operates at two levels. At the provincial level, PPHI Sindh manages central procurement by selecting rates, products, and suppliers. At the district level, District Offices order supplies based on local needs from these pre-selected suppliers. Before payment, District Offices verify deliveries and check quality reports from the Drug Testing Laboratory. The supply management system includes built-in flexibility. District-level warehouses store and distribute supplies to health facilities monthly. For urgent needs, District Offices can share supplies with neighboring districts that have surplus stock.

¹ 'Section 42' companies are not-for-profit entities that can receive public funding while maintaining operational autonomy from government bureaucracy

KEY BOTTLENECKS

The diagram below identifies the key bottlenecks within the province's supply financing and procurement processes in Sindh. It shows how interconnected challenges within each phase of the diagrams presented above progressively constrain the flow of EMHS from procurement to delivery at the health facility. This is pictorially represented by the "flow" of funding and supplies getting pinched at each of these bottlenecks and the color of the flow becoming more faint as the challenges mount. This represents less EMHS ultimately being made available to patients at health facilities via stockouts, often leading to patients having to pay out-of-pocket (OOP) to obtain the EMHS they need from alternative sources like drug shops.

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Weak capacity at the facility level for monthly supply requests

- ⓘ This request usually matches with the available stock at the DHOs; not in line with the actual needs of health facilities.
- ⓘ Inadequate quantification of actual needs at facility-level creates shortages of medicines

Lack of dedicated EMHS or financing tracking system

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- ⓘ No integrated financing or EMHS tracking system at the PHC facility, hospital, or DHO levels
- ⓘ DHOs usually receive information from health facilities without DDOs through DHIS monthly reporting

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Alternative EMHS supply processes have accountability issues

- ⓘ Although local purchase is done through the multi-membered committees – there are often issues of corruption and low-quality supplies

BUDGETING FOR MEDICINES AND SUPPLIES

In Sindh, the purchase of medicines and drugs made up around 8% of the total health budget in FY 2023-24 (Figure 3). Looking at previous trends, the annual allocations for medicines and supplies have consistently increased in nominal terms with an upward trend over the past four years, increasing from PKR 14.37 billion in FY 2020-21 to PKR 29.08 billion in FY 2023-24 (Figure 1). However, the real value of these allocations shows that despite nominal increases, the purchasing power hasn't grown as substantially as the numbers might suggest.

While the Director General Health Services at Hyderabad provides top-ups for additional support, they represent a very small fraction of the total budget for medicines and supplies. This suggests that these might have been targeted funding mechanisms for specific needs rather than significant supplementary funding. Further, the disaggregated financial data is not publicly available for dedicated budgets of medicine and supplies under the overall single-line grant of PPHI Sindh, which caters to the needs of most PHC facilities of the province.

Lastly, budget data for the past 4 years show that budget allocation for medicine and supplies has increased about 23.5% in real terms. Further, the utilization rate is more than 90% relative to the allocation as well as releases for the medicine budget.

Figure 1: Annual Purchase of Medicines and Drugs in Sindh, FY 2020 to 2024, PKR Millions~

~ Please note that the chart does not show the DG Top-Up as that amount is very small in Sindh (please see table below), instead we have shown the Total amount spent by Sindh province annually from FY 2020 to 2024 and the inflation adjusted amount with base year 2023-24.

PKR Millions	Purchase of Medicines and Drugs	DG Top-Up	Total	Inflation Adjusted 2023-24*
2020-21	14,252.24	121.66	14,373.90	23,553.42
2021-22	20,878.16	0	20,878.16	29,769.74
2022-23	25,834.62	112.81	25,947.43	29,406.98
2023-24	29,078.98	0	29,078.98	29,078.98

* Inflation adjusted with base year 2023-24, being the latest year of analysis.

Source: Finance Department – IMU, Govt. of Sindh. Inflation from World Bank's CPI Data.

Figure 2: Utilization of Medicines Budget

Expenditure as a % of Total Allocation, PKR Billions, Nominal

Figure 3 : Share of Medicines and Drugs from Sindh's Total Health Budget for FY 2024-25

Allocation as a % of Total Health Budget, PKR Billions

Sindh Health Budget FY 2024-25	PKR billions	
Total	336.78	
Non-Salary	163.53	49%
Salary	108.91	32%
Development	37.08	11%
Purchase of Drugs and Medicines	27.26	8%

Recommended Citation:

Obaid Khan, Jeewat Rai, and Anooj Pattnaik. 2025. "Financing Essential Medicines and Supplies in Sindh Province in Pakistan." Financing Supplies Factsheet 5. Karachi: ThinkWell.

This is part of a series of factsheets on this topic within lower-and-middle-income countries (LMICs) under the Strategic Purchasing for Primary Health Care (SP4PHC) project. SP4PHC is a project that ThinkWell is implementing in partnership with government agencies and local research institutions in six countries, with support from a grant from the Gates Foundation.

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